

Using Multi-Mode Fibers to Increase the Tolerance to Pointing Errors in Seamless FSO Links

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Abstract: We investigate the advantages of using a multi-mode fiber (MMF) instead of a single-mode fiber (SMF) in seamless FSO-fiber links, demonstrating that the resilience to pointing errors can be roughly doubled. © 2022 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Free Space Optics (FSO) communications are becoming very attractive for ultra-high-capacity seamless fiber-wireless transmission in 5G and beyond communication systems, mainly due to their huge available and free-license spectrum [1]. However, one of the main challenges associated with this technology lies in the very high directivity of the optical beam, which results in pointing errors, requiring the development of highly accurate acquisition, tracking, and pointing (ATP) mechanisms for the optical beam alignment [2].

2. Free-Space Optics Link with Multi-Mode Fiber

For optimal communication, it is necessary to guarantee that the transmitter (Tx) and the receiver (Rx) are well-aligned, to avoid the pointing errors and the angle of arrival (AoA) impact. The challenge of creating a fully autonomous alignment system for the joint optimization of the Tx and the Rx depends on the power feedback received on each side. However, the starting point for the alignment process might be very challenging due to the absence of a measurable received optical power if the initial pointing error is too high. A proficient algorithm will quickly converge to the optimum system alignment in just a few iterations when the first power threshold is found. However, the search for this value can be very slow and the success rate can be compromised. In this work, we investigate the impact of the pointing errors in an FSO link when using an MMF instead of an SMF. A 2D sweep of the beam at the Rx plane is done using two stepper motors, synchronized with a real-time power meter, see Fig. 1. For a 20 mm horizontal and vertical displacement, it can be observed that the MMF area of the optimal power values is larger than the SMF, see Fig. 2. Fig. 3. presents a cut of the power contour map that highlights the width difference between the two fibers. Considering a power threshold of -35 dBm, the tolerated beam misalignment with the SMF fiber is about 1.34 mm, which is doubled with the MMF fiber to about 2.71 mm. The MMF will help to improve the algorithm success rate and its convergence speed since its numerical aperture is larger.

Fig. 1: Experimental setup used for automatic beam alignment.

Fig. 2: SMF and MMF colormaps of power received at Rx for the different beam focus.

Fig. 3: SMF and MMF power penalty of beam misalignment.

3. Conclusion

This work demonstrated the advantage of using MMF to improve the robustness of FSO transmission systems to pointing errors with the objective of finding an optimal power target more easily. However, current fiber-optic communications systems are based on SMF facilitating their integration with the existing systems and subsystems.

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References

- [1] Marco A. Fernandes, Paulo P. Monteiro, and Fernando P. Guiomar, "Free-Space Terabit Optical Interconnects," *J. Lightwave Technol.* 40, 1519-1526 (2022).
- [2] Marco A. Fernandes, Bruno T. Brandão, Petia Georgieva, Paulo P. Monteiro, and Fernando P. Guiomar, "Adaptive optical beam alignment and link protection switching for 5G-over-FSO," *Opt. Express* 29, 20136-20149 (2021).